

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Hand Hygiene among Health Care Workers in a Private Hospital - Questionnaire Based Study

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Abstract

Background: Effective hand hygiene is one of the most important measures to prevent cross-transmission of microorganisms. Improper hand hygiene by healthcare workers (HCWs) is responsible for about 40% of nosocomial infections. Studies have shown that increasing knowledge, behavior and attitudes could enhance hand hygiene compliance in nursing homes thereby reducing the incidence of HCAs. **Objective:** To assess knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding hand hygiene among HCWs in Private Nursing Homes. **Methods:** A cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted among health care workers (HCWs) in Private Nursing Home. Knowledge was assessed using WHO hand hygiene questionnaire. Attitude and practices were evaluated using self-structured questionnaire. **Results:** The study included 42 HCWs from a private hospital, out of 42, 13 were males and 29 were female. 34 % of the HCWs are nursing staff, followed by 26% doctors, 19% technicians, 12% housekeeping and 9% from Reception area. All participants had received training in the hand hygiene practice; 93% participants were aware about 7 steps of Hand washing, 88% have knowledge regarding 5 moments of Hand hygiene laid down by WHO. 78% had missed hand hygiene practices 1 in 5 times, with main reason for not adhering being irritation and dryness caused by hand washing agents and busy schedule. **Interpretation & Conclusion:** This study shows the importance of improving the current training programs targeting hand hygiene practices among HCWs. Hand hygiene training sessions may need to be conducted more frequently with continuous monitoring and performance feedback to encourage them to follow correct hand hygiene practices.

Keywords: Hand hygiene; Nosocomial infections; Health care workers (HCWs).

Introduction:

Healthcare-associated infections is a major problem for patient safety and its surveillance and prevention must be a priority for settings and institutions committed to making health care safer. (1) Healthcare-associated infections are an important cause of morbidity and mortality in nursing homes.(2)

The most effective single measure for infection prevention in various health care settings, including nursing homes is hand hygiene.(3)

The importance of hand hygiene was recognized as early as 1840s, by Dr. Oliver Wendell Holmes to prevent childbed fever and in the late 1840's, by Dr. Ignaz Semmelweis to reduce maternal mortality in a Vienna hospital. However, adherence remains low (40% or below) in most of the health care institutions.(1)

The hands of HCWs may become persistently colonized by pathogenic flora such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, Gram-negative bacilli, or yeast(4). Microorganisms have the ability to survive on hands for differing times.

Improper hand hygiene by healthcare workers (HCWs) is responsible for about 40% of nosocomial infections resulting in prolonged illnesses, hospital stays, long-term disability and unexpected high costs on patients and their families, and lead to a massive additional financial burden on the health-care system.

Several studies have demonstrated the effect of hand cleansing on HCAI rates or the reduction in cross-transmission of antimicrobial resistant pathogens.(4)

Studies have shown that increasing knowledge, behavior, and attitudes could enhance hand hygiene compliance in nursing homes thereby reducing the incidence of HCAIs.

Handwashing with soap and water has been considered a measure of personal hygiene for centuries and has been generally embedded in religious and cultural habits. Nevertheless, the link between handwashing and the spread of disease was established only two centuries ago, although this can be considered as relatively early with respect to the discoveries of Pasteur and Lister that occurred decades later.(1)

The term hand rub refers to “applying an antiseptic handrub to reduce or inhibit the growth of microorganisms without the need for an exogenous source of water and requiring no rinsing or drying with towels or other devices”(1)

Previous research has pointed to individual knowledge deficits influencing safe hand hygiene practices in nursing homes such as correct duration of hand washing and deficits in hand rub recommendations.(5)

It was also shown that the incidences of serious infection could be reduced after the introduction of a multifaceted hand hygiene program to improve hand hygiene adherence and compliance in nursing homes. However, it has been pointed out that the application of hospital infection control guidelines to nursing homes is often unrealistic in terms of system differences and different available resources for infection prevention.(6)

Healthcare workers' hands represent the principal route of transmission of nosocomial pathogens. They are colonized permanently by the physiological flora (“resident flora”) and temporarily, depending on the precise nature of the employee's duties, by various pathogens that do not belong to the physiological flora (“transient flora”). *Staphylococcus aureus*, for example, can survive for over 2 hour on the hands and is found in 10% to 78% of staff.(7)

Objective:

To assess knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding hand hygiene among HCWs in Private Nursing Home.

Methods:

A cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted among health care workers (HCWs) in a Private Hospital, a tertiary health care Centre in Urban area, Bengaluru during Feb to March of 2023, to assess knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding Hand Hygiene. This study included all HCW (42 in number), who come in contact with patients. Knowledge will be assessed using WHO hand hygiene questionnaire. Attitude and practices will be evaluated by using self-structured questionnaire. The participants were explained the need of the study, identity will not be disclosed, and were assured that this survey is only for research purposes.

Results will be calculated using SPSS software. To compare the relationship between variables, the Chi-square test was used and odds ratios (OR) were calculated using logistic regression. A *p* value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

The study includes 42 HCWs from a private hospital, out of 42, 13 were males and 29 were female. Maximum were in the age group of 20-40 yrs. 34 % of the HCWs are nursing staff, followed by 26% doctors, 19% technicians, 12% housekeeping and 9% from Reception area. 36% of HCWs has experience of 1-5 years, while 33% with < 1yr and 31% had >5years of experience. All participants have received training in the hand hygiene practice; 93% participants are aware about 7 steps of Hand washing, 88% have knowledge regarding 5 moments of Hand hygiene laid down by WHO. All participants know the goal of hand hygiene is to reduce HCAIs. 78% had missed hand hygiene practices 1 in 5 times, with main reason for not adhering being irritation and dryness caused by hand washing agents and busy schedule.

**Table 1:
Socio-Demographic Data**

Table 2: Attitude Practice HCWS			Numbers (N=42)	Percentage (%)	Knowledge, And among
Age (yrs)	20-40		38	90%	
	40-60		3	8%	
	>60		1	2%	
Sex	Male		13	31%	
	Female		29	69%	
Occupatio n	Doctor		11	26%	
	Nursing staff		14	34%	
	Technician		8	19%	
	House keeping		5	12%	
	Others (Specify)	4		9%	
Duration as HCW (yrs)	<1YR		14	33%	
	1-5YR		15	36%	
	>5YR		13	31%	
			Numbers(N=42)	Percentage (%)	
Steps in hand washing procedure as per WHO guidelines	10 Steps		--	--	
	3 Steps		--	--	
	5 Steps		3	7	

	7 Steps	39	93
Minimum duration of Hand Rub	20-30 sec	30	71
	60-80 sec	--	--
	2-3 min	10	24
	5-10 sec	2	5
Minimum duration of Hand wash with Soap and water	5-10 sec	1	2
	40-60 sec	35	83
	5 min	2	5
	20-30 sec	4	10
Duration of surgical scrub	40-60 sec	--	--
	3- 5 min	41	98
	20-30 sec	--	--
	30 min	1	2
When Hands are visibly soiled, what to use,	Hand wash with soap	41	98
	Hand rub	1	2
Moments of hand hygiene by WHO	5	37	88
	7	5	12
	3		--
	8		--
Do you wash hands after removal of gloves	Yes	41	98
	No	1	2
Do you do hand hygiene due to compulsion from	Yes	39	93
	No	3	7

infection control team?			
Ultimate goal of hand hygiene is to reduce HCAI	Yes	42	100
	No		--
Have you ever received training in the Hand hygiene practices?	Yes	42	100
	No		--
Do you adhere to correct steps of hand hygiene every time	Yes	41	98
	No	1	2
Main route of cross-transmission of potentially harmful microbes between patients in a health-care facility	Health-care workers' hands when not clean	18	43
	Air circulating in the hospital	2	5
	Patients' exposure to colonized surfaces	17	40
	Sharing non-invasive objects between patients	5	12
How many times hand hygiene practices are missed	1 in 5 times	33	78
	1 in 10 times	6	15
	1 in 20 times	1	2
	1 in 50 times	2	5

	1 in 100 times		--
Reasons for not adhering to hand hygiene practices	Facilities not available	1	2
	Very busy	16	38
	Facilities available but access difficult	4	10
	Facilities available but not in good condition		--
	Handwashing agents causing irritation and dryness	21	50
	Lack of role models among colleagues or superiors		--
	No guidelines/protocols in place		--

Discussion:

Hand disinfection is key to the prevention of nosocomial infections. At Geneva University Hospital, improvement of the compliance rate from 48% to 66% over a 5-year period lowered the frequency of nosocomial infections by more than 40%.(7)

Health care-associated infections constitute one of the greatest challenges of modern medicine. Despite compelling evidence, that proper hand washing can reduce the transmission of pathogens to patients and the spread of antimicrobial resistance, the adherence of health care workers to recommended hand-hygiene practices has remained unacceptably low. Reducing health care-associated infections requires that health care workers take responsibility for ensuring that hand hygiene becomes an everyday part of patient care.

The reasons for poor hand-hygiene practices include lack of scientific knowledge, unawareness of risks, misconceptions (eg, glove use obviates the need for hand hygiene), unavailability of hand-hygiene facilities (sinks or alcohol dispensers), lack of role models among colleagues or superiors, understaffing or patient overcrowding, and lack of institutional priority.(8)

This study attempts to know the HCWs knowledge, attitudes, and practices about hand washing.

Out of 42 HCWs in the study, 34 % are nursing staff, followed by 26% doctors, 19% technicians, 12% housekeeping and 9% from Reception area.

In this study, knowledge among HCWs about steps and moments of hand hygiene practices laid down by WHO was 93% and 88% respectively.

In a study done by Lt V. Anargh et al in Pune, WHO guidelines regarding duration were being followed by 90% for hand washing with soap and water and 64% for alcohol-based rubs(9). In this study, 83%,71% and 98% had good knowledge regarding duration of Hand wash, Hand rub and surgical rub respectively.

98% HCWs practice hand wash with soap and water, when hands are visibly soiled and also wash hands after removal of gloves.

All participants have received training in the Hand hygiene practices and are aware that hand hygiene practice reduce HCAs.

Majority of participants were of the belief that unclean hands are an important route of cross transmission that is same as in a study done by Lt V. Anargh et al in Pune.⁹ 78% of HCWs were missing hand hygiene opportunities 1 in 5 times which is very high compared to 21% as mentioned by Lt V. Anargh et al in Pune. In a study done by Sreejith Sasidharan Nair in Raichur, overall compliance of hand hygiene by HCWs was less than 50%.(10)

Factors that contribute to poor adherence to hand hygiene include poor access to hand washing facilities (sinks), the time required to perform standard hand washing, irritant contact dermatitis associated with frequent exposure to soap and water, high workloads, knowledge deficits among HCWs, and the failure of administrative leaders to make hand hygiene an institutional priority(11).

In this study, main reason for not adhering to hand hygiene practice are irritation and dryness caused by hand washing agents (50%), busy schedule (38%), while in a study done by Lt V. Anargh et al in Pune(9), Heavy workload (38%), non-availability (52%) and inaccessibility (9%) of hand hygiene facilities were the common reasons for non-compliance.

Conclusion:

Evidence-based hand hygiene can prevent transmission of the most important nosocomial pathogens. Compliance could be improved by knowledge of the principal clinical circumstances in which hand disinfection by healthcare workers genuinely benefits the patient.⁷

Strategies to improve hand-hygiene adherence must be multifaceted and include the education and motivation of HCWs, the use of performance indicators, and hospital management support.

Simple training sessions for HCWs should be held on each ward. Inclusion of the goals in the training program, because behavior learned during basic training is put into practice much more effectively than that taught in later training sessions, when established routine behavior has to be changed.

Disinfecting hand rubs should be available where they are actually needed.

Reduction of hand-washing to a minimum in order to avoid unnecessary skin irritation.

Senior members of medical staff must recognize that they have to set an example and act accordingly.

In addition, patients can be educated about the importance of hand hygiene and be encouraged to ask HCWs to comply with hand-hygiene guidelines.

The efficiency of the hand-rub technique can be evaluated with an alcohol product supplemented with fluorescent dye and an ultraviolet light.

Another way to estimate the quality of hand hygiene is to evaluate the consumption of soap and alcohol.

In order to improve patient safety and reduce costs, good hand hygiene should become one of the highest priorities in health care institutions. (11)

Summary - This study shows the importance of improving the current training programs targeting hand hygiene practices among HCWs. Hand hygiene training sessions may need to be conducted more frequently with continuous monitoring and performance feedback to encourage them to follow correct hand hygiene practices.

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